

north american
academic research

Research

Impacts of the Belt and Road Initiative on the Development of Cote d'Ivoire

*Sahui Magby Henri Joel Regis**

*School of International Trade, Jiangxi University of Finance and Economics, P.R China
330013*

**Corresponding author*

Accepted : 25 June, 2019 Published online :28 June, 2019

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3261864>

Abstract: *The Belt and Road Initiative was introduced in 2013 by China to the world. The initiative reached several countries in Africa where several development projects are conducted. Cote d' Ivoire, which is also an African country, accepted to deepen its cooperation with China by joining the well-promoted Belt and Road initiative. The purpose of this paper is to analyze the evolution and impact of the Belt and Road Initiative in Cote d'Ivoire. An investigation of official sources, economic factors, interviews, and SWOT analysis leads to the finding that the Belt and Road Initiative was successfully implemented in Cote d'Ivoire and is contributing to the development of the country. The notion of win-win promoted by China seems to be effective.*

Keywords: *Belt and Road Initiative, development projects, win-win*

Introduction

The Belt and Road Initiative, initially named One Belt, One Road Initiative is a development project initiated by the government of China in 2013, which is mainly orientated towards the following sectors: infrastructure, energy, transport, technology, public utilities; and also investments in countries located in Europe, Asia, and Africa.

The Belt and Road Initiative is motivated by the export capacity of Chinese industries which are seeking for more market shares to satisfy their overproduction and essentially oriented by an important political commitment of the Chinese government for the sake of more interconnections between countries to facilitate trade and investments.

The aim of this project is to reinforce trade, infrastructure and investments nexus between China and 65 other countries of the world accounting for over 30 percent of the global GDP, 62 percent of the world population, and 75 percent of the world energy reserves.

The Belt and Road Initiative comports two roads, the first road is the Silk Road Economic Belt, which is the original silk road including countries located in Central Asia, West Asia,

the Middle East, and Europe. The second road is Maritime Silk Road which links to China countries located in South East Asia, Middle East, Africa, and Europe.

In recent years, it was announced that the Belt and Road Initiative was open to all countries and organizations around the world.

The Belt and Road Initiative has been very active on the African continent. Numbers of projects such as roads and railways, seaports aiming a better connection of African countries are financed by China. Reaching the coast of East Africa via the Suez canal, the maritime silk road is intended to go through several African countries with the final objective to link the eastern part of Africa to the central, western and southern parts of the continent.

In this context of Belt and Road Initiative in Africa, Cote d'Ivoire which is a major country in West Africa has also benefited considerable projects, as promoted by the initiative.

The present paper analyzes the changes brought by the Belt and Road Initiative into the country.

It explains some factors related to the Belt and Road Initiative which are the Chinese presence in Cote d'Ivoire, the economic growth, the Chinese investments, the volume of trade and shows their evolution since the Belt and Road Initiative was launched.

2. Brief Introduction on Cote d'Ivoire

Cote d'Ivoire is a country located in West Africa, neighbored by Ghana, Guinea, Mali, Liberia, and Burkina Faso. It is an essential country in the West African region as its economy represents 40% of the West Africa economic and monetary union's (WAEMU) GDP and 63% of the industry in that area. Its economy is intensely subject to agriculture and related activities. Cote d'Ivoire is the world's top cocoa producer, largest cocoa beans exporter, and also a major actor in the production and export of coffee and palm oil.

Cocoa, coffee, and oil are the country's best export source of income, however, the nation has focused on the processing of cocoa, cashews, mangoes, and different items as a high need. Besides agriculture, mining gold and electricity export are the most developed activities.

After a decade of political instability that ended in 2011, the country has encountered consequent foreign investments and GDP growth; and for the past five years, the GDP growth rate of Cote d'Ivoire was classified among the highest in the world. The country remains the most attractive country of the West African region in terms of foreign investments. In 2017, Cote d'Ivoire collected 25.8% of the WAEMU's foreign investments and was ranked 5th Africa's fastest growth according to Quantum Global,

Figure 1: GDP growth rate of Cote d'Ivoire from 2010 to 2017

Source: World Development Indicators

3. The Belt and Road Initiative in Cote d'Ivoire

The Belt Road Initiative was launched in the year 2013 which was also the 30th anniversary of diplomatic ties between China and Cote d'Ivoire.

During the anniversary ceremony, officials from both countries reaffirmed the good relations existing between the two countries and announced incoming projects, as earlier mentioned by the Ivorian president saying that in the coming years, investments of about 5 US\$ billion will be made by the Chinese government in Cote d'Ivoire in order to build socioeconomic infrastructures.

According to the Economic Bureau of the Chinese Embassy in Cote d'Ivoire, citing the Chinese Ministry of Commerce, the total value of "the new contracts in 2015 ".signed between the two countries were in the amount of US\$ 1.2 billion, contrarily to US\$ 185 million in 2014.

The same source also mentioned that Chinese investments roughly reached US\$ 3.88 million during the year 2015.

In 2017, the key elements of the partnership between China and Cote d'Ivoire were divulged by the Chinese foreign minister Wang Yi. He announced that over ten projects worth US\$2.5 billion were being analyzed at that moment and once accepted the total value of Chinese projects in Cote d'Ivoire would exceed US\$7 billion

Although several projects were financed by China in Cote d'Ivoire under the Belt and Road initiative, Cote d'Ivoire officially joined it in 2018 by signing 18 agreements worth US\$ 3.4 billion with China

After the African summit held in Beijing in September 2018 where a good number of agreements were signed, 9 contracts on infrastructure projects worth US\$ 5 billion have been financed by China.

The Belt and Road Initiative in Cote d'Ivoire, as shown above, is illustrated by huge investments made by China mainly in infrastructure and energy projects as defined in the initiative objectives.

Here follows a nonexhaustive list of the Belt and Road Initiative projects in Cote d'Ivoire:

Table 1: Nonexhaustive list of the Belt and Road Initiative projects in Cote d'Ivoire

Project	Amount
Extension of the autonomous port of Abidjan	US\$ 800 million
Grand Bassam Highway	US\$ 104 million
The Olympic Stadium of Ebimpé	US\$ 140 million
Construction of four ultra-modern high schools	US\$ 28 million
Renovation of the Ivorian road network	US\$ 76 million
Strengthening the national power grid	US\$ 819 million
Soubré Hydroelectric Dam	US\$ 572 million
San Pedro Thermal Power Plant	US\$ 2 billion
Extension of Abidjan Airport	EUR 64 million
The dry port of Ferké	EUR 457 million

4. Impact of the Belt Road Initiative on Cote d'Ivoire

In order to analyze the impact of the Belt Road Initiative on Cote d'Ivoire, some factors towards which our research will be oriented have been selected. These are the following axis:

- Chinese presence in Cote d'Ivoire
- Chinese investments in Cote d'Ivoire

- Trade volume between China and Cote d'Ivoire
- SWOT Analysis of the Belt Road Initiative in Cote d'Ivoire

4.1 Chinese presence in Cote d'Ivoire

The Chinese presence in Cote d'Ivoire is analyzed through two points: the physical presence and business presence.

4.1.1 Physical Presence

In order to obtain information related to the physical presence of Chinese citizens in Cote d'Ivoire, a short survey was made by interviewing individuals living permanently in diverse cities in Cote d'Ivoire, Ivorians students and workers in China but who recently came from Cote d'Ivoire, and also Cote d'Ivoire residents who to China for a short period of time for business or work purpose.

The general answers which recurrently were given by the interviewees mentioned that Chinese citizens are more visible than before. They can be easily seen in shopping malls, streets, touristic places and also at their workplace, building roads and other infrastructures and energy projects.

4.1.2 Business Presence

The business presence of Chinese citizens in Cote d'Ivoire, according to the same interviewees is very effective. It can analyze in two axes: small businesses and big enterprises. The small businesses such as restaurants, shops, clinics, printing shops are increasingly appearing in the Cote d'Ivoire market, in Abidjan and other big cities. However, the research of market shares pushes them to go more and more to remote areas where commodities are scarce. The big enterprises are the ones realizing the different projects signed with the government.

Some private enterprises are also operating in Cote d'Ivoire as confirms the recently created chamber of Commerce of Chinese enterprises in Cote d'Ivoire with about 40 member companies whose activities cover ports, industries, hydroelectric dams, public works, transport, energy, infrastructure construction. Also, the Ambassador of China in Côte d'Ivoire announced that in 2018, 15 to 20 new Chinese companies will be permanently established in Côte d'Ivoire, especially in the industrial zone of Pk24. Meanwhile, a new industrial zone developed by a Chinese company is being constructed in Abidjan.

4.2 Chinese Investments in Cote d'Ivoire

The Chinese investments in Cote d'Ivoire have drastically soared after the year 2013 which is the year of creation of the Belt and Road Initiative. The investments rose from US\$ -4.79 million in 2013 to 24.26 US\$ million the following year, reached 60.24 and 56.53 US\$

million in 2015 and 2016 and doubled to 112 US\$ million in the year 2017. The change is impressive and attests the good relationship between the two countries.

Figure 2: Chinese FDI in Cote d’Ivoire from 2010 to 2017 in Million of US Dollars

Source: China Ministry of Commerce (MOFCOM) Statistics (2018)

4.3 Trade Volume between China and Cote d’Ivoire

As one of the aims of the Belt Road Initiative is to reduce trade barriers, an evident consequence would be an increase in the trade volume between China and the countries joining the initiative.

In the case of Cote d’Ivoire, the volume of trade with China has considerably increased from the year 2013.

Figure 3: Trade volume between China and of Cote d’Ivoire from 2010 to 2017 in Thousands of US Dollars

Source: International Trade Centre (ITC) statistics

Due to the lack of data, a direct impact of the Belt Road Initiative on the GDP growth rate of Cote d'Ivoire, Chinese FDI in Cote d'Ivoire and trade volume between Cote d'Ivoire and China can't be found. Therefore we can only observe the evolution of the variables.

And the observation of the graphs of 3 variables (Figure 1, Figure 2, Figure 3) shows a common point which is a considerable increase starting from the year 2013, which is the beginning of the Belt Road Initiative.

Table 2: Detailed trade volume between China and Cote d'Ivoire

Years	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Imports	545703	460538	715818	1423653	980543	1113826	1486746	1303487
Exports	79445	116090	108870	151636	143240	95193	71367	117213
Trade Volume	625148	576628	824688	1575289	1123783	1209019	1558113	1420700
Imports change (%)	8.93	-15.6	55.43	98.88	-31.12	13.59	33.48	-12.33
Exports change (%)	44.97	46.13	-6.22	39.28	-5.54	-33.54	-25.03	64.24
Trade Growth (%)	12.48	-7.76	43.02	91.02	-28.66	7.58	28.87	-8.82

Source: Author's computation of data collected from the International Trade Centre (ITC) statistics

The observation of figure 3 and table 2 shows that trade between the two countries considerably increased starting from the year 2013. We can also notice that Cote d'Ivoire imports much more from China and its exports to China gradually increased.

4.4 SWOT Analysis of the Belt Road Initiative in Cote d'Ivoire

For a better understanding of the Belt Road Initiative in Cote d'Ivoire, a SWOT analysis appears to be indispensable. The results of the analysis are presented in the following paragraph:

Strength

The Belt Road Initiative is instigated by the Chinese government and accepted by the government of Cote d'Ivoire which accelerate the different processes related to doing business in Cote d'Ivoire. Also, the initiative is supported by huge financial funds generated by financial bodies and institutions such as the Asian Investment and Infrastructure Bank (AIIB), BRICS New Development Bank, Silk Road Fund.

Weakness

The weakness of the Belt Road Initiative in Cote d'Ivoire for the Chinese companies operating on the territory mostly lies in cultural differences, different manners, and habits, as attest several conflicts between Chinese and local workers frequently happening in Cote d'Ivoire and also in some other countries in Africa.

Also, the interest rate of the Belt Road Initiative loans between 2 to 3 percent is much more expensive than those proposed by the Japanese, that seems to be at 0.25-0.75 percent.

Opportunities

The opportunities created by the Belt Road Initiative are quite significant. They are defined in two points: opportunities for China and opportunities for Cote d'Ivoire.

Opportunities for China

The Belt and Road Initiative fosters the development and increase of the Chinese companies, creating a path which leads to more market shares.

The Belt Road Initiative also gives broad and direct access to natural resources to China, for instance, the recent investment of 24.4 million of Euros from the Chinese firm China National Geological & Mining Corp in a manganese mine.

Opportunities for Cote d'Ivoire

The Belt and Road Initiative gives a plethora of opportunities to Cote d'Ivoire which are illustrated as follows:

Jobs opportunities created by Chinese firms and factories.

Also, through the creation of jobs appears technological transfer which surely leads to more competition on the Ivorian market.

The development of infrastructures such as roads, seaport, buildings definitely improve living conditions and facilitate trade and transport which definitely impact positively the social welfare of the population of Cote d'Ivoire.

The Belt and Road Initiative in Cote d'Ivoire creates also more export and business opportunities for local enterprises which is demonstrated by the increasing level of exports to China.

Threats

An essential threat of the Belt and Road Initiative in Cote d'Ivoire is the perception of debt-trap that a lot of people have about it. Indeed, a certain opinion based on cases that happened in other countries doesn't really appreciate the Chinese initiative. An illustrative example is the case of Sri Lanka handing a major port to China in 2017, for the failure of its debt payment.

An identical situation seems happening in Zambia where according to Richard Krah (2018), China was proposing to cease the Kenneth Kuanda International airport in case of payment failure of the huge debt. The consequence of this situation caused a cancellation in 2018 of a Belt and Road Initiative project in Sierra Leone over an airport construction and also a rejection of US\$ 3.1 Billion Chinese loans by the Kenyan president.

Another major threat is the competition with western companies established for years in Cote d'Ivoire, especially those from the former colonizer country (France).

These countries use their strong links into the country and also their Media as powerful instruments to protect their market shares.

This last aspect of the threats to the Belt and Road Initiative in Cote d'Ivoire tells about a certain bad image that a part of the population of Cote d'Ivoire has about Chinese products and companies. The reason is the fact that many low-quality products imported from China such as fake rice, fake medicines have been sold in the country, and also the fact that some Chinese companies don't generally respect environment, flora, and fauna.

5. Conclusion

The Belt and Road Initiative is significantly contributing to the development of Cote d'Ivoire through the impressive projects which were realized and are effectively planned to be.

The impact of the Belt and Road Initiative seems to be positive for both Chinese and Ivoirian's sides in the short run.

On the Chinese side, more companies and businesses are operating in Cote d'Ivoire which means more market shares and profits. On the other side, Cote d'Ivoire is benefiting of the construction of major infrastructures, experiencing a considerable increase of Chinese investments which obviously creates more jobs for its population. Its exports to China have also increased and the trade volume as well.

However, the risk of debt-trap potentially exists and several African countries are getting aware. The government of Cote d'Ivoire should carefully manage this situation to avoid damaging consequences for the country. As the Belt and Road Initiative is at its early stage in

Cote d' Ivoire, predictions on any outcome are hard to make. We can rather only wish a good end to each side of the initiative, as they both seem satisfied for now.

References

1. AfriqueMonAfrique (2018) Kenyan President Kenyatta Rejects \$ 3.1 Billion Chinese loan
2. Amani Georges (2017) la Chine prepare 10 grands projets de developpement avec la Côte d'Ivoire (Côte d'Ivoire News)
3. C Dong, M. Davis, S. Yu (2018) China's One Belt One Road: Opportunities in Africa
4. CCI France Cote d Ivoire (2016) L'Economie Ivoirienne en bref et les principaux secteurs d'activités
5. CIA World Factbook (2018) Cote d'Ivoire Economy 2018
6. Connection ivoirienne.net (2018) Ouattara rentre de Chine avec un “chèque” record de 1 900 milliards de Fcfa pour la Côte-d’Ivoire
7. Dipanjan Roy Chaudhury (2018) Africa cancels a Belt and Road Initiative project for the first time (the economic times)
8. Donatien Kautcha (2018) Côte d'Ivoire : Le port sec de Ferké, la centrale thermique de San Pedro et l'extension de l'aéroport, les retombées de la visite de Ouattara en Chine, (Koaci.com)
9. Fiacre E. Kakpo (2017) Côte d'Ivoire-China: a portfolio of projects worth over \$7 billion (Ecofin Agency)
10. Jayanna Krupakar (2015) Geopolitics of China’s Belt and Road Policy. (Indiandefencereview)
11. Jean-Mermoz Konandi (2017) Côte d’Ivoire : le chinois CGM va investir 16 milliards FCFA dans sa mine de manganèse de Lauzoua (Financial Afrik)
12. Julia Breuer (2017) Two Belts, One Road? The role of Africa in China’s Belt & Road initiative
13. Kay Schultz (2017) Sri Lanka, struggling with debt, hands a major port to China (The New York Times)
14. Lisa (2017) Côte d'Ivoire : les investissements chinois en hausse (ministère du Commerce) (French.china.org.cn)
15. Mamadou Kanate (2017) Un point sur les investissements de la Chine en Côte d'Ivoire (French.china.org.cn)

16. Ouestaf (2018) Investissements : la Côte d'Ivoire, pays le plus attractif d'Afrique de l'Ouest (Indice)
17. Sylvain Vidzraku (2018) La coopération entre la Côte d'Ivoire et la Chine se renforce (la tribune afrique)
18. World bank group (2018) Belt and Road Initiative
19. Xinhua (2012) China to invest about \$5 bln in Cote d'Ivoire in coming years
20. Xinhua (2017) Côte d'Ivoire : création d'une chambre de commerce des entreprises chinoises pour renforcer la coopération sino-ivoirienne

ANNEXES

Annexe 1: Belt and Road Initiative routes

Source: Indiandefencereview (2015)

© 2019 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA . Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

